

TABLE—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	%M	%N	%loss in wt. at 120°	Cond.*	μ_{eff} in B.M. (Temp.)
[Gd(HO-PhBzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₂ ·2H ₂ O	C 19.67 F 19.38	12.26 12.40	4.50 4.82	128	8.07(306.5°K)
[Tb(HO-PhBzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₂ ·2H ₂ O	C 19.85 F 19.69	12.23 12.44	4.49 5.06	125	9.46(306.5°K)
[Dy(HO-PhBzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₂ ·1.5H ₂ O	C 20.42 F 20.35	12.32 12.41	3.39 3.62	118	10.73(307.5°K)
[Ho(HO-PhBzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₂ ·H ₂ O	C 20.90 F 20.73	12.42 12.63	2.28 2.45	117	10.55(306.5°K)

HO-PhBzH=C₁₁H₁₀N₂O* Electrical conductance in ohm⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ in DMF at 305°K

C=Calcd.; F=Found.

The bands identified as due to transitions from the ⁵I₈ ground level to ⁵I₆ (8.55, 8.68 kK), ⁵I₅ (11.28 kK), ⁵F₆ (15.27, 15.43 kK), ⁵F₄ (18.62 kK), ⁵F₃ (20.66 kK), ³K₃ (21.28 kK) and ⁶G₆ (or ⁵F₁; 22.12 kK) levels of Ho(III) in the present complex suffer practically no shift from positions in LaCl₃-host⁷.

The general trend suggests that the extent of covalency decreases with increasing number of electrons in the *f*-orbital.

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Complexes of Pd(II) with Thiohydrazide

Derivatives

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THE complexes of some acet-thiohydrazides and acet-thiohydrazones with Ni(II) are known¹⁻⁴.

In previous communication, complexes of oxovanadium(IV) with some thiohydrazide derivatives have been reported⁵. In the present note, preparation and characterisation of complexes of Pd(II) with acet-thiohydrazides namely, phenylthiohydrazide (pthH), *p*-anisidylthiohydrazide (athH), furfurylthiohydrazide (fthH), *o*-hydroxyphenylthiohydrazide (*o*-hthH) and *p*-hydroxyphenylthiohydrazide (*p*-hthH) are reported.

Experimental

The ligands were prepared as reported in the literature⁶. Palladium(II) chloride was obtained from Johnson and Mathey Ltd. The complexes PdL₂ (L=deprotonated ligands) were prepared by the following general method: an aqueous PdCl₂ solution (0.2 g in 100 ml; pH~2) was treated with a 2% ethanolic solution of the ligand in requisite proportion when a cream yellow complex separated immediately. The product was digested on a steam bath for about 20 min, filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried in an air oven between 80 and 90°.

The results of elemental analysis and important ir bands are recorded in Table 1. The palladium(II) was estimated as dimethylglyoximate after decomposing the complex with conc. HNO₃ and perchloric acid. Physical measurements were done as reported earlier⁵.

Results and Discussion

Thiohydrazides (A) has been found to coordinate as monoanionic ligand in thiol tautomer (B) with Pd(II) in neutral,

(R=phenyl-, *p*-anisidyl-, furfuryl-, *o*-hydroxyphenyl- and *p*-hydroxyphenyl groups).

alkaline and even acidic medium forming *bis* chelated neutral complexes PdL₂ (LH=pthH, athH, fthH, *o*-hthH or *p*-hthH). Excepting *p*-hydroxyphenylthiohydrazide complex [Pd(*p*-hth)₂], other *bis* chelates are separated out almost quantitatively from aqueous or aqueous ethanolic medium. The complex [Pd(*p*-hth)₂] is slightly soluble in water but dissolves appreciably in ethanol, methanol etc. whereas other *bis* chelates are almost insoluble in water as well as organic solvents like methanol, ethanol and benzene. Almost all the complexes are fairly soluble in DMF. The complexes are diamagnetic supporting their planar stereochemistry with

TABLE I

Compounds	%Metal Found (Reqd.)	%Nitrogen Found (Reqd.)	IR Bands in cm^{-1}						$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})/\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$
			$\nu(\text{NH}) + \nu(\text{OH})$	$\delta(\text{NH}_2)$	$\beta(\text{NH}_2)$	Thioamide Bands			
						I	II	III & IV $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$	
Pd(pth)	25.91 (26.05)	13.62 (13.71)	3060br (3220sbr)	1612s (1598s)	1490m (1476s)	1575m (1530s)	1390w (1375s)	722sh (1010sbr, 840s)	
Pd(ath) ₂	22.30 (22.72)	12.08 (11.95)	3188s, 3115s (3248br, 3185m)	1602s (1603vs)	1465m (1460m)	1570s (1530m)	1408m (1386s)	960s, 706m (940s, 840s)	422m, 345s
Pd(fth) ₂	27.19 (27.37)	14.81 (14.42)	3095m (3230m, 3170m, 3130m, 3105w)	1610m (1580s)	1470sh (1475s)	1560w (1540br)	1390s (1390s)	1010m, 708w (1005s, 820m)	456m, 336m
Pd(o-hth) ₂	24.00 (24.15)	12.62 (12.72)	3200s (3275sbr, 3235mbr)	1615m (1605s)	1480s (1465s)	1560s (1515br)	1375s (1365mbr)	700m (1000vs, 820vs)	
Pd(p-hth) ₂	22.49 (22.33)	11.88 (11.76)	3000br, 2400br (3030br, 2390br)	1580br (1575s)	1435br (1440mbr)	1530sh (1500br)	1370m (1375m)	715br (1012s, 830sbr)	403m, 335m

s=strong ; w=weak , m=medium ; br=broad and sh=shoulder.
The ir bands in paranthesis are those of the free ligands.

dsp² covalent bonding. The electronic absorption spectra of DMF solutions of the complexes do not display ligand field bands in visible region, they rather display strong absorption below 420 nm which probably envelopes the ligand field band expected for Pd(II) in square planar environment.

Free thiohydrazides display two to three distinct ir bands (Table I) in 3μ region due to $\nu(\text{NH})$, $\nu_s(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\nu_{as}(\text{NH})$ vibrations⁷. In complexes, the coordinated thiohydrazides display only a broad and medium band between 3100 and 3250 cm^{-1} . The $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ vibration of thiohydrazides is not affected appreciably but the $\beta(\text{NH}_2)$ is shifted to higher wavenumber indicating the involvement of hydrazine part terminal nitrogen in bond formation^{8,9}. Free o-hthH and p-hthH display a broad and medium band near 2650-2350 cm^{-1} attributable to hydrogen bonded phenolic OH which are retained in their Pd(II) complexes indicating that phenolic group is not involved in coordination with Pd(II) ions. The ligands possess potential thioamide group and therefore display characteristic thioamide bands (I to IV) in the region 1550-770 cm^{-1} . The thioamide bands I and II are raised to higher frequencies while thioamide band IV mainly due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ is shifted to lower frequencies indicating the bonding of thiocarbonyl sulphur by deprotonation of thiol tautomer of the ligands^{10,11}. In far infrared region, the complexes display two to three medium to weak bands assignable to Pd-N and Pd-S vibrations. The energy of these bands are well within the range expected for $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$ vibrations^{12,13}.

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Studies on Rh(III) and Pt(IV) Complexes of Schiff Bases

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COMPLEXES of Rh(III) and Pt(IV) with the Schiff bases, N-4-methylphenacylidene anthranilic acid (MPAA) and N-4-methylphenacylidene-o-aminophenol(MPAP) have been isolated and assigned octahedral structures on the basis of analytical, magnetic, electronic and ir spectral data. Electronic spectral studies indicate that the ligand field bands observed for Rh(III) complexes are analogous to those observed in Pt(IV) complexes.

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